

SPED referral flowchart¹

Below is an exemplar SPED referral flowchart, adapted from a typical referral flowchart used in UK schools. Its key assumptions are:

- Access to a SPED specialist;
- Access to relevant medical/psychological specialists where appropriate.

¹ **Citation for this document:** Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021fc). *Implementation Planning: SPED Referral Flowchart* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Implementation Planning Tool No. 3). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743613>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/TJZEP4QS>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. Commissioned by the Organization of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia. ([details](#))